

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Testing the predicted performance of recombinant inbred lines in rice using triple test cross (TTC) design, Basic Generations, and F₃ families

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We predicted the performance of recombinant inbred lines of three crosses by obtaining estimates of m (midparent value) and D (additive genetic variance) from TTC design, Basic Generations, and genetic parameters from F₃ families (Table 1). We only discuss 1,000-grain weight and panicles per plant out of several characters studied.

From each of the crosses, 90 inbred lines were produced using single-seed descent procedure. We measured the characters that we predicted.

The actual and predicted values were very close (Table 2). In cross A, the actual percentage of lines produced was

Table 1. Estimates of m and D obtained from TTC and basic generation families and from F₃ families for 1000-grain wt and panicles per plant for crosses A, D, and E.

Source	1000-grain wt (g)			Panicles (no./plant)		
	A	D	E	A	D	E
			\hat{m}			
TTC and Basic Generation	25.6	29.4	40.1	21.3	16.6	17.5
F ₃	26.5	28.8	29.3	25.8	18.9	19.7
			\hat{D}			
TTC and Basic Generation	6.0	2.8	4.9	19.6	19.2	14.9
F ₃	3.9	4.4	3.3	15.2	14.4	5.7

Table 2. Predictions (% better than better parent) and recombinant inbred lines actually produced from crosses A, D, and E.

Item	1000-grain wt (g)			Panicles (no./plant)		
	A	D	E	A	D	E
TTC predictions (%)	13	3	10	5	49	4
F ₃ predictions (%)	17	3.8	0.7	24	41	3
Lines produced (%)	13	12	13	29	20	24

very close to the predicted values. In cross D, the actual percentage of lines produced in both cases was much closer to the F₃ predictions than to the TTC predictions. In cross E, for both characters, more superior inbred lines were produced than predicted.

The results indicate that the two sets of predictions agree reasonably well.

The actual number of superior inbred lines produced agreed the best with F₃ predictions. F₃ families, which are grown for all crosses in rice breeding programs, can be used as an accurate alternate source of genetic parameters to predict the outcome of crosses early in breeding programs. □

Breeding methods

Effect of maltose and gelling agent on protoplast culture response in indica rice

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Indica rices have a relatively lower response to protoplast culture than japonica rices. We manipulated the culture medium to improve the plating efficiency of suspension-derived protoplasts of IR72.

Cell suspension was initiated from mature seed and maintained in liquid N₆ medium with 5 mM proline, 2 mg 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)/liter

Table 1. Effect of osmotic concentration of maltose on the viability of cells in culture.

Maltose (% wt/vol)	Duration (d) of protoplast viability in culture ^a
9	4.8 d
11	8.5 c
13	>28.0 a
15	13.8 b

^aAv of 4 replications over time. Mean separation by DMRT at 5% level. One replication consisted of 3 plates with 1.5×10^5 protoplasts per plate.

and 30 g maltose/liter. Protoplasts were isolated from 5- to 6-mo-old cell suspension and plated in 1.5 ml medium

Table 2. Effect of type of gelling agent on the plating efficiency of IR72 protoplasts.

Gelling agent	Plating efficiency ^a (%)
Agarose VII	0.67 b
Sea plaque agarose	0.88 a

^aPlating efficiency = $\frac{\text{no. of colony-producing protoplasts}}{\text{total no. of protoplasts plated}} \times 100$ (%)

Av of 4 replications over time. Mean separation by DMRT at 5% level. One replication consisted of 3 plates with 1.5×10^5 protoplasts per plate.

solidified with 6 g agarose VII (Sigma)/liter at 1×10^5 protoplasts/ml. The gel was bathed in 4-ml liquid medium with